

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING BIOETHICS COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Annotation: This thesis highlights the current aspects of the process of forming and developing bioethical competence in future educators. It analyzes the pedagogical conditions, didactic tools and methodological approaches to the formation of a bioethical culture that meets the requirements of modern education. Bioethical competence includes skills such as understanding ethical criteria in pedagogical activity, loyalty to humanitarian ideals, and a responsible attitude towards life and the environment.

Keywords: future educator, bioethics, bioethical competence, moral education, methodology, innovative education, responsibility, professional training.

Introduction.

The socio-spiritual changes and globalization processes taking place in the education system in the 21st century put on the agenda the need to train pedagogical personnel who will work professionally based on the principles of humanitarianism, moral responsibility and bioethics. Especially taking into account the social significance of pedagogical activity and the degree of its impact on the individual, the formation of bioethical competence of future teachers is considered one of the important directions of the modern educational process.

Bioethics is a science formed at the intersection of medicine, biology and moral values, and at present it is also gaining relevance in pedagogical activity. Because through bioethical approaches, it is possible to develop respect for human life, ecological awareness, moral responsibility, and commitment to personal and social values. In this regard, bioethical competence is a type of professional competence based on the integration of moral, legal, ecological, psychological and professional knowledge, skills and values. It serves to ensure a faithful approach to human dignity, life, rights and values in the professional activity of the teacher.

The development of bioethical competence of future teachers is carried out through the use of modern didactic approaches, innovative educational technologies and goal-oriented methodological systems. This, in turn, requires the development of educational methodological approaches that ensure the

harmony of cognitive, affective and psychomotor components. At the same time, by teaching bioethics issues in the educational process on the basis of an integrative approach, it is possible to develop professional awareness and ethical standards in students. The thesis analyzes the mechanisms of formation of bioethics competence, pedagogical conditions and methodological tools that serve to develop this competence. The relevance of the research is that it is inextricably linked with the goals and objectives set out in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education”, the “Strategy of National Development until 2030” and the principles of “New Uzbekistan - New Education”.

Today, a deep understanding of the essence of bioethical competence in pedagogical activity and its effective formation are becoming one of the main requirements of the teaching profession. This competence includes not only professional knowledge and skills, but also personal and psychological factors such as moral reflection, empathetic thinking, sociocultural responsibility. Therefore, the development of bioethical competence in the process of training future teachers is not a single method, but a process that requires a complex, multi-stage and integrative approach. First of all, in order to form bioethical competence from a methodological point of view, it is necessary to develop educational strategies that ensure the harmony of cognitive (knowledge), affective (value) and conative (behavioral) components. These components serve to form the moral and legal thinking, professional responsibility, humanitarian and ecological consciousness of the teacher. For example, the cognitive component involves the acquisition of theoretical knowledge in the field of bioethics in pedagogical activities - the principles of bioethics, human rights, moral dilemmas, and the concepts of environmental safety. The affective component, on the other hand, represents the attitude to this knowledge with personal and social values - that is, an axiological approach.

To form this competence in the educational process, it is important to teach students to think based on life problems using interactive methods - “brainstorming”, “cluster”, “idea palette”, “role play” techniques, as well as socio-pedagogical cases. In particular, in an “ethics laboratory” environment, directing students to discuss complex situations related to bioethics (for example, artificial life extension, ecological destruction, the balance of man and technology) develops their moral and analytical potential.

In methodological approaches, integrative models for the formation of bioethics competence based on training modules are proposed. This model takes into account the following stages: 1) Motivational preparatory stage - arousing

the student's interest in the bioethical issue; 2) Information-analytical stage - mastering theoretical knowledge on the topic and reinforcing it with practical examples; 3) Interactive analysis stage - discussing ideas and values through various didactic exercises; 4) Reflective-resultative stage - understanding changes in oneself, being able to express one's opinion independently.

Also, the development of bioethical competence through the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in the modern educational process requires special attention. In this regard, virtual simulations, interactive multimedia tools, online ethical quizzes, electronic cases bring students face to face with bioethical problems and encourage them to think independently. The methodological foundations of developing bioethics competence are associated with a modern educational strategy, in which the teacher is considered not only as a provider of knowledge, but also as a subject who instills educational and axial values, and shapes cultural and ethnic thinking. This, in turn, requires the widespread introduction of new curricula, interdisciplinary integration, and axial-axiologically oriented methods in the training of future teachers.

Discussion:

In modern pedagogical practice, the formation and development of bioethical competence is one of the important indicators that determine not only the professional, but also the moral and psychological readiness of the teacher. This competence includes elements such as an axiological approach to pedagogical activity, ethical decision-making, professional reflection, ecosocial responsibility, and interactive communicative potential. In the discussion, the main attention is paid to the need to reinterpret the content and essence of the pedagogical process based on the principles of bioethics.

Analysis of the research results shows that the traditional knowledge-based approach to the formation of bioethical competence of future teachers is not sufficiently effective. On the contrary, an integrative-pedagogical approach, that is, teaching bioethics issues in an inextricable link with the disciplines of general pedagogy, psychology, ecology, law, and ethics, provides high efficiency. Through such an approach, metacognitive thinking is formed in students, that is, the skills of critical analysis and evaluation of ethical issues and reflective attitude towards one's own behavior. Also, the discussion emphasizes the practical expression of bioethics competence in pedagogical activity, that is, the skills of compliance with professional and ethical standards, the manifestation of empathy and tolerance in interpersonal communication, and the management of students' moral socialization. Practical research shows that specially developed

training modules, case studies, and seminars based on ethical dilemmas play an important role in the formation of moral sensitivity and ethical awareness in students.

According to the results of pedagogical experience, students strive to apply the acquired bioethical knowledge in real situations, in which the approach of contextual analysis - that is, solving each problem based on its social, cultural and legal situation - was effective. Through such reflective approaches, students develop a responsible attitude towards life, nature, society and human rights.

During the discussion, another important issue is the exemplary role of the teacher. The moral and spiritual position, life values and professional ethics of the future teacher directly affect not only himself, but also the personal formation of students. Therefore, the need for methodological systems based on the concept of education focused on axial values in the training of teachers is discussed. Based on the above, it can be said that the methodology aimed at developing bioethical competence should be considered not only as a means of professional training, but also as a means of developing human qualities, moral stability and social cohesion. This strengthens the importance of education at the modern stage of pedagogy not only as a provider of knowledge, but also as a formative of personality.

Conclusion.

The formation and development of bioethical competence in the process of training future teachers is one of the priority strategic tasks of today's education. The results of the study show that in order to develop this competence, it is necessary to abandon traditional knowledge-oriented approaches and introduce innovative, interactive and integrative methodological systems that serve to develop the student's personal-axial values.

Bioethical competence in pedagogical activity is directly related to factors such as humanity, environmental sustainability, adherence to ethical standards, social responsibility in society, and commitment to professional ethics. Therefore, the content and forms of pedagogical education should be fundamentally revised in the formation of this competence. The methodological model developed during the study is aimed at the harmonious development of the cognitive, affective, and conative components of bioethical competence in the pedagogical process, and its effectiveness has been confirmed on the basis of practical experience. It was found that the formation of the image of a teacher as a personal example in pedagogical activity - a teacher who adheres to bioethical values, demonstrates tolerance and empathy - is of particular importance, and

serves to increase educational effectiveness. In general, an improved methodology for the formation of bioethical competence in future teachers serves as an important factor in ensuring not only the quality of education, but also the spiritual and moral orientation of the pedagogical process. In the future, it is recommended to conduct large-scale applied research in this area, improve curricula for bioethics competencies, and integrate them into the national education system

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